

Causes of Burnout and Its Impact on Job Psychological Motivation among Correctional Officers at Six Prisons in Nyanza Region of Kenya

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Abstract:

Burnout refers to feelings of work burden including psychological fatigue which frequently result from a gradual pile of daily stresses. It is a psychological word for the undesirable reaction towards prolonged job connected stress. Many research studies have shown that correctional officers around the world, including Kenya, experience significant levels of burnout. The reported research sought to examine how burnout affects the psychological motivation of correctional officers in their job. A significant amount of research has been conducted by scholars on burnout and psychological work motivation. However, only a few studies have investigated the link between burnout and psychological work motivation among these

individuals in Kenya. The study was to examine the causes of burnout, among correctional officers working in six Medium Prisons within Nyanza Region of Kenya. This study employed a descriptive and correlational research design utilizing a survey method. The study incorporated both quantitative and qualitative approaches and was guided by the principles of Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory and Solution Focused Theory. The target population was 1,910 prison officers attached to six Medium prisons in Nyanza region of Kenya. The prison facilities included: Kisumu Medium Prison in County of Kisumu, Nyamira Prison in County of Nyamira, Migori Prison in County of Migori, Siaya Prison in County of Siaya, Kisii Main Prison in County of Kisii and Homa Bay Prison in County of Homa Bay. The researcher categorized correctional officers into various types of ranks, such as gazetted officers, inspectorate officers, non-commissioned officers, and constables. In this study, the research employed the Maslach Burnout Inventory- Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) and the Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS) as instruments for measurement. The researcher realized that within the medium prisons, officers who are deployed to work directly with the inmates are male officers whereas the female officers are deployed to work in the offices hence the sample population was totally men. It also came out that there was no big difference in the responses from different facilities and therefore the findings were handled generally. The study found out that the main cause of burnout in this region is chronic work conditions and job position reported by 80.4% and was followed by poor public image at 35.71% whereas 10.71% acknowledged other factors as the cause of burnout. The research suggests that it would be beneficial for prison management to employ trained counselors and establish effective systems for addressing burnout among correctional officers. It is also important to enhance the overall atmosphere within the organization by implementing measures such as acknowledging and rewarding employees, offering opportunities for advancement, and creating a reliable internal ombudsperson role to address any unjust administrative practices in the institution.

Keywords: *Burnout, Job psychological motivation, Causes of burnout, Correctional Officers.*

Introduction

In 1974, Herbert Freudenberger first came up with the concept of burnout, which refers to a state of lacking optimism and enthusiasm towards work (as mentioned by Kristiana et al., 2016). It's currently a main mental wellbeing issue midst workforces and a source of monetary loss and mental distress. According to Mondy (2016), burnout is a feeling of burden including mental and physical exhaustion which commonly result from a regular accumulation of everyday stress. According to Sukmana & Sudibia, (2015), burnout is characterized by three components which include emotional exhaustion, lack of personal accomplishment and depersonalization

Prison officers are accountable not only for the custody of prisoners but also supervision, enforcement of rules and regulations of the prison, prevent disturbances, escape and keeping up security and safety. They also guide, mentor and guard inmates alongside preventing contraband items from entry into the prison (Ministry of Home Affairs [MOHA], 2015). Their duties depict role conflict and role ambiguity putting them in a tight spot of treatment or enforcement which also cause burnout as indicated by Griffins, Morgan & Lin, (2012).

A number of studies have been conducted among correctional officers and have established that burnout is prevalent among them (Griffins, Hogan & Lambert, 2012). In USA, the federal bureau of prisons agree that working in a correctional facility is stressful and can lead to burnout hence affecting individuals who work in such settings (Griffins, Morgan & Lin, 2012). Correspondingly, Torch and Ciofas (2012) conducted a study in Canada and found out that 60% of correctional personnel considered their profession to be at least reasonably demanding and 34% reported experiencing indicators of burnout.

Another study conducted by Tabassum (2013) among Israeli prison officers found the intensities of burnout to be greater than that of police officers. This seems to put forward that unlike police officers who have a short-term encounter with prisoners owing to limited time between apprehension and trial, prison officers spend very lengthy time with offenders due to their long sentences. Since most of the prisoners are violent, correctional officers encounter problematic people for an extended period of time. According to Griffins *et al.*, (2012), from shift to shift; the correctional officers are tasked with keeping watch over the irrational prison subculture. Contact with the subculture on a daily basis causes burnout in the professional life of correctional officers. Many studies point to both individual and structural factors as specified by Leiter & Maslach (2014).

A set of undesirable attitudes and conducts are developed by the officers leading to a trend to handle beneficiaries disconnectedly or a skeptical obsession with enjoyment of oneself all of which institute the depersonalization element of burnout which are seen as self-protective coping tools (Obiora, 2012). In a different study conducted in Canada among correctional officers, it was established that prison work is a dull tiresome work and job short of variety thus cited as the second and third causes of burnout respectively after poor management due to routine (Torch & Kiofas, 2012).

Research has been conducted in Bulgaria on burnout syndrome among employees in panel institutions. A large number of officers at the District Prison in Plovdiv were found to have a high occurrence of the syndrome. Burnout syndrome was more prevalent among young, unmarried, and highly educated officers, and it typically appeared within the initial 5 years of their service. The results indicate that it is important to develop and put into practice effective strategies to decrease and prevent the rise of burnout syndrome. The District Prison in Plovdiv observed a significant occurrence rate of

74.53% among its employees. The research found that all three sections of burnout had a high occurrence rate. The stress phase accounted for 48.11% of the total, followed by the resistance phase at 66.98%, and finally, the exhaustion phase occurred at 41.51%. The job role within the hierarchy of the service organization was found to be a reliable indicator of stress level during a particular phase. Nearly 80% of the well-educated employees experienced significant levels of burnout syndrome, which became apparent within the initial five years of their employment at the prison.

According to Obiora (2012), the prison structure in Nigeria has been associated with underperformance as a result of burnout coming from chronic situations such as inmates who spit, urinate or empty the bowels into a container and fling them at correctional officers who are on duty. Prison officers are exposed to many hours of shouting and curses, these infuriated outbursts from inmates are likely to provoke other offenders into similar behaviour thus providing a tough environment for officers to work in. Such inmate's behaviours towards prison officers may result in amplified levels of burnout as argued by Tabassum (2013).

In South Africa, Thandi (as cited in Gitau, 2013) conducted a study on burnout among South African correctional officers and found that high levels of burnout is correlated with the existence of several physical and psychological hitches such as depression, anxiety, suicide, alcohol abuse, isolation from others, self-neglect, cardiovascular problems and psychosomatic disorders such as stomach ulcers, high blood pressure and heart disease.

A study in Kenya among prison personnel in Kamiti Maximum Prison showed that causes of burnout affecting the personal accomplishment recording the uppermost at 49.2% (Gitau 2013). Several research carried out in penal institutions indorsed intensely that structural effects together with individual level variables, apply the utmost influence on workers experience.

According to Mondy (2016), burnout is conveyed with job withdrawal, absenteeism,

intention to leave and high turnover. Those who keep to their job regardless of burnout face reduced job output and efficiency decreases, develop lesser job contentment which cause decline in their job performance. Population in the prisons swell every day instigating overcrowding in penal institutions, forcing correctional officers to multitask by for example monitoring the feeding of prisoners, conducting security searches, ensuring the security of inmates, averting escape or any jeopardy and also watching over fellow prison officers as a security measure exposing the officers to burnout as stated by (Griffins, Hogan & Lambert 2012).

A big number of previous panel institution burnout studies have concentrated on the prevalence and influence on job performance, and it has been found that burnout has adverse outcomes for both staff and correctional institutions.

Prevalence of burnout among panel officers has brought about psychological difficulties to correctional officers which may perhaps affect their work. In Kenya, only one study on prevalence of burnout among correctional officers has been conducted so far by Gitau (2013) and it revealed that burnout was prevalent. This research aims to examine how common burnout is in various correctional facilities in order to determine the extent of burnout levels.

According to Casio (2018), motivation originated from the Latin term "movere" which translates to "move". It is described as a strong drive that is influenced by the needs, wants, and desires of employees. Its purpose is to motivate workers to dedicate their full focus and effort to achieve the desired objectives of the organization.

Zubir (2018) explained that many research studies have attempted to explore the link between employee psychological motivation and absenteeism. These studies consistently find a negative correlation between psychological motivation and job absenteeism. In other words, when an employee's psychological motivation is high, their likelihood of being absent from work is low, whereas when their motivation is low,

their absenteeism tends to be high. This correlation showed that there was a link between a lack of psychological motivation and absenteeism.

Statement of the Problem

Worldwide, signals demonstration that burnout can lead to diminished work performance and decreased quality of service. In Kenya, very few studies have been done on burnouts across various professions. A study by Kokanya (2004) which focused on the level of burnouts among medical workers at Kenyatta National Hospital documented a high prevalence of 94.5%. Nganga (2008) assessed the prevalence of burnouts midst accountants at University of Nairobi and this study showed a prevalence that ranged from 27.4% to 72.6%. The only available study in Kenya on burnout among correctional officers revealed a high burnout prevalence at Kamiti Maximum prison (Gitau, 2013). This study by Gitau (2013) showed that little shared support at work place, poor work relationships, high work load and job stress were associated with these burnouts. Current reflection of correctional personnel in Kenya also portrays psychological hitches owed to pointers such as misuse of drug and substance, job slackness, nonattendance, sick offs and cases of fights with prisoners and colleagues (MOHA, 2015).

The Information available on burnouts specifically among prison officers in Kenya, is therefore scarce and rudimentary. These available studies on burnout among correctional officers have not focused on its impact on job psychological motivation. In prisons within Nyanza Kenya, informal reports from the Prison Commandants and prison officers reveal a high prevalence of burnout and job related stress (Personal Communication). This situation warranted this to be an important study by investigating how burnout impacts job psychological motivation among correctional officers within this region.

Causes of Burnout among Correctional Officers

Correctional officers are answerable for safe custody of inmates and responding to emergency or crisis situations in correctional

settings. Study shows that their work is described by numerous psychological stressors that vary by degree of intensity which may lead to burnout.

According to Griffins *et al.*, (2012), burnout is higher in correctional work than many other occupations including the police who are their counterparts in law enforcement. Some of the causes of burnout are explored below.

Chronic Work Conditions and Job Position

Chronic conditions such as scarce housing, poor housing, poor sanitation and oppressive responsibilities are strong stressors instigating burnout among correctional officers (Chen *et al.*, 2013). Job position in a correctional institutes has been allied with burnout as well. Related studies have revealed that those in care positions as well as treatment positions reported higher levels of burnout (Carson & Thomas, 2016).

Griffins *et al.* (2012) indicated that correctional environments take their toll on correctional officers as they pass through the gates. As they march into the prison they are immediately hit by the smell of bodies being housed together in cells and wards, the noise of voices struggling to be heard from the blocks, the sound of footsteps and the feeling of violence looming around. Literally they are on guard all the time they enter the prison gate since they are locked within the prison for around eight hours.

According to a study conducted by Frank and Hyden (2017), working as a correctional officer is perceived as one of the most dangerous occupations. They may be subject to potential risks and hazards in their work and institutional settings, as well as impacts on their mental and physical well-being. They essentially intervene in prison riots, dismantle prison gangs, and safeguard themselves against infectious diseases.

The report also mentioned that correctional officers have the responsibility of intervening in inmate conflicts, inspecting inmate cells, evaluating their meals, and safeguarding their coworkers against assaults by prisoners. A study conducted on 106 correctional officers working in three prisons within the Australian correctional system utilized a Likert scale consisting of five items to measure

dangerousness. The findings revealed that dangerousness had a significant and direct impact on burnout among the officers (Carson & Thomas, 2016).

According to Andra (2019), correctional officers experience frequent exposure to violence and distressing situations, as well as daily interactions with dangerous inmates, resulting in high levels of job-related stress that often leads to burnout. It is anticipated that they will handle the emotional distress and internalize it as a requirement of their role, with the purpose of maintaining a positive reputation for the organization. Displaying vulnerability in this line of work might be perceived as a lack of success, inadequacy, a detrimental impact on their career, or an opportunity for an incarcerated individual to assault them. In the year 2016, inmates at Cook County Jail in Illinois carried out 500 assaults against prison officers. Additionally, he highlighted that prison officers often witness inmates engaged in acts of violence, such as murdering one another, participating in extensive brawls, deliberately igniting their cells, or even taking their own lives.

In line with Frank & Hyden's (2017) findings, law enforcement officers face difficulties related to depression and hopelessness. They also encounter sleep disturbances, nightmares, and burnout caused by post-traumatic stress disorder resulting from traumatic incidents in their line of work. As a way to cope with these psychological issues, they often turn to alcohol or drugs, which unfortunately do not alleviate their problems.

Gitau (2013) reported that a study was piloted by Thandi on the causes and degree of burnout amongst correctional officers in one of the South African prisons. It publicized that 28% of the respondents intensely approved the view that being exposed to dangerous prisoners causes burnout. Chen *et al.* (2013) found out that daily interaction with inmates and the prison environment are constantly reported as causes of burnout, the routine staff-inmate interactions in particular is the most important contributor. Obiora (2012) posited that inmates do not want to be confined and employ all manner of tricks and manipulations to make their circumstances

of imprisonment as relaxed as possible therefore supervising them cause burnout to the prison officers.

A study by The American Addiction Centre (2018) revealed that prison officers have the second highest mortality rate of any profession in America. It further found out that extreme stress, depression and workplace injuries are some of the daily challenges causing burnout among correctional officers thus influencing them to use drugs and alcohol to get through the dehumanization of their work conditions.

Whiteacre (2013) contends that the prison setting presents an unequal danger of being exposed to contagious illnesses, including airborne diseases like tuberculosis as well as blood borne pathogens such as hepatitis B, C, and HIV. Inmate crowding in units lead to burnout alongside restrictions of movement on duty which involve physical restriction during work and rest period (Carson & Thomas, 2016).

According to Masango (2016), there is also risk of unconscious displacement of aggression by inmates as psychological ego defense mechanisms whereby the prison officers may become targets of aggression that is really meant for someone else who is out of site. It was outlined by Obiora (2012) that prisons in Nigeria are in deplorable, unfavorable and harsh conditions, the environments are mostly hot, overcrowded, lice infested and noisy thus stressful causing burnout to prison officers manning the penal institutions.

According to Papa (2015), prison warders staged a nation-wide protest in 2008 reporting poor work conditions in Kenyan Prisons. In agreement with the correctional officers, an investigative report by a committee of specialists led by Honorable Major Retired Marsden Madoka in July 2008 specified a long list of ills such as disease, filth, incompetence and modern slavery.

The study seeks to assess the impact of burnout on job psychological motivation among correctional officers in Kenya particularly Medium Prisons in Nyanza region so as to study a different culture altogether. Several causes have been identified, most of which are their

working environments. This current study further investigated causes of burnout among correctional officers in Medium Prisons in Nyanza region of Kenya.

Role Ambiguity

The role of a correctional officer can also cause burnout particularly when coupled with the changing political scenery that can engulf this sometimes penal and other times rehabilitative occupation. Ukwendi & Ushi (2014) defines role conflict as a struggle of officers to merge custodial duties with their treatment functions.

Role ambiguity can be described as a situation in which there is a lack of clarity or uncertainty about the responsibilities and expectations related to a job.

This can occur when there is a discrepancy between the information provided to an employee and what is actually necessary for them to effectively perform their job. Role ambiguity is more strongly related to job psychological dissatisfaction compared to role conflict, and this dissatisfaction is a component of burnout, according to Petita and Veccione (2012).

Torch and Klofas (2012) state that professionals in this field may face conflict due to their role, as they are responsible for enforcing existing laws. However, it is important for them to not let their emotions or personal opinions influence their decisions, as juggling both roles can be incredibly challenging and can result in significant stress. It will eventually lead to exhaustion and burnout if this stress continues. Another factor that can contribute to burnout is the presence of role confusion and ambiguity at work, leading to uncertainty about job expectations.

In the research conducted by Kristiana et al. (2016), the concept of role conflict was defined as having conflicting pressures at the same time, making it unfeasible to adhere to one without ignoring the other. Role conflict often arises when an individual's own beliefs and principles clash with those of their supervisor or the overall organization.

Multiple studies consistently show that role conflict is associated with negative consequences, including decreased job

satisfaction, frustration, loss of trust and respect, lack of confidence in the organization, ethical challenges, and increased stress levels leading to burnout.

Poor Public Image

The perception in public domain of correctional officers as described in movies and literature is one of corrupt, incompetent and ruthless officers who maltreat and abuse prisoners; this has made many officers to feel they are a stigmatized minority and are often uncomfortable or cautious to disclose their profession due to poor public image (Petita & Veccione, 2012).

Cecil (2018) reported that the public view correctional officer's work and particularly their roles as undesirable, bad media attention on staff transgression including sexual assault, inappropriate relationships, introduction of smuggled goods such as drugs and mobile phones into the prison and arrests by police for non-job related crimes have influenced the public view of correctional officers thereby causing burnout among them.

Working as a prison officer has low social status as noted by Torch & Klofas (2012) in a study of Israeli correctional officers which established a strong relationship between poor social status and burnout. More burnout indicators were reported among correctional officers when the community's view towards them was worse. The study further reported that the status of the job is also poor in the eyes of the inmates due to comments by inmates that they don't actually have any respect for a regular guard who just carries the keys.

Low public acknowledgment and poor public image of the occupation is therefore related to burnout, this is demonstrated by the fact that most correctional officers reported that their current job is their second choice as noted by (Petita & Veccione, 2012). He further reported that correctional officers chose to work in prison rather than be jobless. As noted by Ukwendi & Ushi (2014), correctional work was regarded as a job of last option after previous job let-downs and people with higher education were significantly less likely to view correctional work

positively or contemplate joining the career due to the impression that it is “dirty work”. Public image of correctional officers is not very favorable due to the perception that they use force on prisoners.

Arguably, correctional officers in California received the lowest job scores among seven criminal justice positions of attorneys, judges, probation officers, parole officers, public defenders and police (Griffins *et al.*, 2012). Chen *et al.* (2013) also reported that a survey on occupational status revealed that correctional officers ranked below police officers and slightly above blue collar jobs such as carpenter and truck driver, this pointed that public view of the job was poor.

Griffins *et al.* (2012) conducted a study to evaluate the level of interest among individuals in becoming prison officers in California. It was found that around two-thirds of those surveyed stated that they were highly unlikely to accept a position as a correctional officer. Only 11% and 3% of respondents expressed a moderate or high likelihood, respectively, of taking on such a job if it were available. The research found that prison work is not highly valued by the general public.

Obiora (2012) maintains that prison officers are regarded as common key keepers who are less educated and inferior to the police and other state security organizations. He further pointed out that a study of prison officers of Freetown Central Prison in Sierra Leone found out that majority of the officers were ashamed of their job. Some reported that they cannot put on their uniforms out of the prison because the public will look at them as marginalized and desperate.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by two theories in the following manner.

Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory

Rational emotive behaviour therapy (REBT) was developed and promoted by Albert Ellis, an American psychologist. Ellis drew inspiration

from the teachings of proponents from various regions, including Greece (McMahon, & Vernon 2010). This text describes the initial version of cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), which was created by Ellis in the mid-1950s. Ellis continued to develop this form of therapy until his death in 2007, as mentioned by Velten, (2010).

This proposition is abecedarian to this study since according to Ellis (2003), one of the main objects in REBT is to demonstrate to the client that every time nasty and unfortunate cranking events do in people's lives, they've a choice to either make themselves feel healthier, sad, displeased, worried, and angry or make themselves feel unhealthier and tone- defeating, depressed, shocked, panicked, tone- abhorring and tone- aching

The theory was therefore found relevant since it shows how people have the ability to be what they want to be without the environment. It was of great help to the researcher to explain what makes the correctional officers feel the way they feel and how they can also change their feelings to be better.

The framework of REBT suggests that individuals possess both inherent rational and irrational inclinations. REBT suggests that individuals, both knowingly and unknowingly, create emotional obstacles such as self-blame, hurt, guilt, shame, sadness, and anxiety, as well as behavioral patterns like avoidance, withdrawal, and addiction through their irrational and self-destructive thoughts (Ellis, 2001). This theory simplified the process of assisting correctional officers in recognizing that individuals make choices and have the capacity to make either positive or negative choices.

Solution Focused Theory

Solution-Focused Therapy was developed in the late 1970's and early 1980's at the Brief Family Therapy Center in Milwaukee by De Shazer and Berg (De Shazer, *et al.* 1986). It came into existence when De Shazer and Berg noticed that clients would openly discussing their troubles and concerns being unable to perceive their own inner self strengths for overcoming these issues

and bowing down to them instead of focusing on what lies ahead.

According to a study conducted by Maljanen et al, (2012), it has been demonstrated that Solution-Focused Brief Therapy (SFBT) has shown efficacy in diminishing symptoms of depression, anxiety, and mood disorders among adult individuals. The objective of Solution-Focused Brief Therapy (SFBT) is to assist individuals experiencing difficulties in discovering immediate tools that can help them in effectively managing symptoms and addressing challenges promptly.

It is based on the belief that even though individuals might have the skills to make changes in their lives, they often require assistance in effectively utilizing and enhancing those skills. By introducing this idea into the study, it became more manageable for correctional officers to handle the working conditions at correctional facilities by making use of the resources they already have. This also assisted them in refraining from fixating on current issues and focusing more on what lies ahead.

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive survey and correlational research methods to carefully examine and explain phenomena, and also explore the link between burnout and motivation in the workplace. The design of this study allowed for the examination of various factors that impact job-related behaviors, and it also provided insights into the depth of the relationship between the variables under investigation (Orodho, 2012).

According to Kothari (2012), correlation research design defines the frequency with which a variable occurs or its association with other variables. Correlation therefore helped the researcher in looking at the association between the independent and dependent variables in the case of establishing the impact of burnout on job psychological motivation of correctional officers in the six targeted Prisons within Nyanza region of Kenya.

The study used a descriptive design to determine how common burnout is among correctional

officers. This type of design allows researchers to gather data and analyze it to understand the relationship between different variables, as shown in the conceptual framework. By using this design, the study provided a current and accurate snapshot of burnout among the population being studied, thanks to the strong external validity of descriptive surveys.

Target Population

The population refers to a specific group or collection of individuals that are important to a researcher and relevant to the specific issue at hand (Hair, 2003). This involves specifying the group of individuals from which our sample is selected. Based on Salkind's (2008) perspective, population refers to the entirety of certain groups. Sekaran and Bougie (2010) also back up this idea, as they define population as the complete set of individuals that the researcher aims to study. The sample for this study included a total of 1,910 correctional officers sourced from 6 Medium Prisons in the Nyanza region.

This encompassed various designations within the correctional system, including gazetted officers, members of the inspectorate, non-commissioned officers, and constables. The prison facilities consisted of Kisumu Medium Prison located in Kisumu County, Kisii Main Prison situated in Kisii County, Homa Bay Prison found in Homa Bay County, Nyamira Prison situated in Nyamira County, Siaya Prison located in Siaya County, and Migori Prison situated in Migori County.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample that accurately represents the target population is selected by researchers in order to estimate unknown characteristics of the entire population and draw conclusions about it based on a smaller subset of data. This approach allows for generalizations to be made with confidence, as explained by Orodho (2012).

Sampling Size

The sample size for primary respondents was calculated using Yamane (1967) formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N \cdot (e)^2} \quad (1)$$

N - The population size

e - The acceptable sampling error

95% confidence level and $p = 0.5$ are assumed

According to Yamane, the researcher used 331 as the sample size considering 95% confidence level and where the precision level was 5%. Each prison facility therefore constituted of correctional officers in a proportional way to the number of the establishment during the study. Siaya Prison 34, Kisumu Medium 112, Migori Main 56, Nyamira Prison 45, Kisii Main 59 and Homa Bay prison 27 accordingly.

The study utilized the stratified random sampling method. To determine the levels and distribution of burnout and job psychological motivation among different ranks, a stratification was conducted based on the officers' positions. This involved categorizing officers into constables, non-commissioned

officers, inspectorate officers, and gazetted officers.

The researcher utilized proportional sampling in order to select a sample of officers. This method of sampling is employed when there are several subgroups in a population that differ significantly in size. The proportion of participants from each subgroup is determined based on their respective population sizes

This increased the likelihood of representativeness because, stratified sampling is a simple random sampling technique applicable in this case because, the population does not constitute a homogeneous group but can be divided into several sub populations that are originally more homogeneous than the total population. To obtain a representative sample, the sample was calculated by $nh = (N_h/N) n$ (Kothari, 2012).

Where nh is the proportionate sample

N_h is the population of strata, n is the sample size,

N is the target population.

Table 1. Proportionate Sample in Kisumu Medium Prison

Strata	Population (N _h)	Proportionate Sample (N _h)
Gazetted Officers	16	3
Inspectorate Officers	32	6
NC O	87	15
Constables	507	88
Total	642(N)	112(n)

Table 2. Proportionate Sample in Siaya Prison

Strata	Population (N _h)	Proportionate Sample (N _h)
Gazetted Officers	1	1
Inspectorate Officers	13	2
NC O	46	8
Constables	135	23
Total	195(N)	34(n)

Table 3. Proportionate Sample in Migori Main Prison

Strata	Population (N _h)	Proportionate Sample (N _h)
Gazetted Officers	4	1
Inspectorate Officers	17	3

NC O	58	10
Constables	247	43
Total	326(N)	56(n)

Table 4. Proportionate Sample in Kisii Main Prison

Strata	Population (Nh)	Proportionate Sample (Nh)
Gazetted Officers	7	1
Inspectorate Officers	14	2
NC O	41	7
Constables	280	49
Total	342(N)	59(n)

Table 5. Proportionate Sample in Nyamira Main Prison

Strata	Population (Nh)	Proportionate Sample (Nh)
Gazetted Officers	1	1
Inspectorate Officers	15	3
NC O	24	4
Constables	212	37
Total	252(N)	45(n)

Table 6. Proportionate Sample in Homa Bay Main Prison

Strata	Population (Nh)	Proportionate Sample (Nh)
Gazetted Officers	1	1
Inspectorate Officers	5	1
NC O	13	2
Constables	131	23
Total	153(N)	27(n)

Instruments of Data Collection

The tools used for gathering primary data in this study are called data collection instruments. Questionnaires was utilized to gather information and allowed the researcher to understand the respondent's opinions on various issues (Kothari, 2012).

In this study, questionnaires comprising of questions on personal data and questions relating to burnout and job psychological motivation were used. Orodho (2012) argues that questionnaires in general are needed to ensure uniformity, cost effectiveness and time saving, the instruments effectively collected data from the correctional officers. The surveys included revised editions of the Maslach Burnout Inventory- Human Service Survey and the Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale.

Social Demographic Questionnaire (SDQ)

The researcher created and utilized this tool to gather information about individuals' personal data, including age, gender, marital status, educational background, job position, and length of employment. This allowed the researcher to collect information on the varying demographic makeup of participants.

Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI-HSS)

The inventory, which was developed by Maslach and Jackson in 1981 (as mentioned in a study by Kristiana et al. in 2016), was designed to assess burnout among professionals in the field of human services, including correctional officers. The text suggests that there were 22 items or statements focusing on personal feelings or attitudes. Each point on the frequency scale was labeled. A value of 1 is given if the respondent

has never experienced the feeling or attitude described and a value of 7 if the person experiences it often. Dimensions of burnout which are emotional exhaustion with higher scores in the 9 items (2, 3, 4, 7, 9, 14, 15, 17 & 21) corresponding to greater experienced burnout, 28 or over is high, 18-27 is moderate while 1-17 is low. Depersonalization presents greater degrees of experienced burnout if the 5 items (6, 11, 12, 16 & 23) score high. 14 or over is high, 8-13 is moderate while 1-7 is low. For personal accomplishment, lower scores in the 8 items (5, 8, 10, 13, 18, 19, 20 & 22) correspond to greater experienced burnout. 40 or over is high, 33-39 is moderate while 1-32 is low.

Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS)

The authors of this scale are Gagne, Forest, Vansteenkiste, Crevier-Baud and Van den Broeck (2015). This set of questions contains 19 items that were employed to assess different aspects of psychological motivation towards work among the officers.

The main focus of the questions was to determine the reasons behind the officers' willingness to exert effort in their current job and was accompanied by the scale 1= *not at all*, 2= *very little*, 3= *a little*, 4= *moderately*, 5= *strongly*, 6= *very strongly* and 7= *completely*.

Gagne et al. (2015) designed in a way that items 1 to 3 measures amotivation with scores of 1-8

low, 9-20 moderate and 21 and over is high for all the components except introjected motivation. 4 to 6 represent extrinsic motivation (social), 7 to 9 extrinsic motivation (material), 10 to 13 introjected motivation which has 4 items therefore scores of 1-11 is low, and 12-27 is moderate while 28 and above is high. 14 to 16 identified motivation and 17 to 19 intrinsic motivation. Higher scores in each dimension correspond positively while lower scores are negative.

Piloting

The researcher carried out a pilot test to guarantee validity and reliability of the study tools. The officers attached to Kakamega Main Prison working directly with the inmates were used for the pilot study since it consisted of a sample with similar characteristics to the main population of the study. From a population of 351 correctional officers, a sample of 10% of the population was selected to participate in the pilot study. (Source: Kakamega Main Prison staff sheet, 2022).

The researcher documented the time of completion and how well the questions were understood by the respondents. The researcher conducted the pilot test twice in a span of two weeks thereafter the tools were adjusted and restructured with the help of my supervisors and other experts

Results

Table 2. Demographic Information of the Correctional Officers in the Targeted Six Prisons in Nyanza Region

Socio-demographic characteristics		Frequency (n= 280)	Proportion (100%)
Age	20 – 24	32	11.4%
	25 - 29	38	13.6%
	30 – 34	36	12.9%
	35 – 39	68	24.3%
	40 – 44	51	18.2%
	45 – 49	30	10.7%
	50 and above	25	8.9%
Gender	Male	280	100%
	female	00	00%

Years of service	1 – 5	35	12.5%
	6 – 10	50	17.9%
	11 – 15	45	16.1%
	16 – 20	60	21.4%
	21 – 25	40	14.3%
	26 – 30	30	10.7%
	31 and above	20	7.1%
Level of education	Primary	10	3.5%
	Secondary	147	52.5%
	College	50	17.9%
	Undergraduate	63	23%
	postgraduate	10	3%
Current rank	Costable	230	82.1%
	Nco	33	11.7%
	Inspectorate	12	4.3%
	Gazeted officers	5	1.9%
Years served in current rank	1 – 5	30	10.7%
	6 – 10	41	14.6%
	11 – 15	48	17.1%
	16 – 20	94	33.6%
	21 – 25	27	9.6%
	26 – 30	25	8.9%
	31 and above	15	5.6%
Marital status	Single	44	15.7%
	Married	195	69.6%
	Separated	20	7.1%
	Divorced	9	3.2%
	widowed	12	4.3%

The researcher tried to find out gender of the respondents in the study and the verdict was that all the respondents were male 280 which signifies 100% due to the type of the prison facilities that were under the study. In the medium prisons where the inmates are males, female officers are not deployed to work directly with the inmates but work in offices.

The sightings in the figure 2 above exposed that 67.9% (190 Respondents) of them had worked below 20 years. While 32.1 % (90 Respondents) had worked for over 21 years as correctional officers.

The findings in the figure 3 above shows that 3.5 % (10 respondents) of the officers had primary education, 52.5 % (147 respondents) of the prison officers had secondary education, 17.9% (50 respondents) had college education while the remaining 26.1% (73 respondents) were university graduates.

The findings from the table above reveals that 82.1 % (230 respondents) of prison officers were Constable, 11.7% (33 respondents) were Non-

commissioned officers, and 4.3% (12 respondents) were members of the Inspectorate while the remaining 1.9% (5 respondents) were Gazette officers.

The results above displays that 25.3% (71 respondents) of the prison officers have served between 1-10 years in the same rank, 50.7% (142 respondents) have served between 11-20years in the current rank. Another 18.2% (52 respondent) have served between 21-30years in the current rank while 5.6% (15 respondents) have served in their current ranks for more than 30years.

The findings above discloses that the highest number of the officers are married at 69.6% (195 respondents) while the single officers were at 15.7 % (44 respondents). Divorced officers were the least in numbers at 3.2 % (9 respondents) followed by the widowed at 4.3% (12 respondents). Separated officers were at 7.1% translating to 20 respondents.

Causes of burnout

The objective of the study was to examine the causes of burnout among correctional officers in Nyanza Region of Kenya. The results are recorded in table 3.

Table 3. Causes of Burnout

Causes Of Burnout	Frequency	Percent
Chronic work conditions and job position	150	80.4%
Poor public image	100	35.71%
Role Ambiguity and role confusion	00	00%
Any other factors	30	10.71%

Discussion

Table 3 above shows that 80.4% (150 respondents) indicated that chronic work conditions and job position was a cause of burnout among prison officers. Some 35.71% (100 respondents) mentioned that poor public image caused burnout among the officers. While 10% (30 respondents) felt that burnout was caused by other factors which they didn't specify. None pointed at role ambiguity as a cause to burnout.

Chronic Work Condition and Job Position

Griffins et al., (2012) concurred that correctional environments takes their toll through the gate. As they walk in to prison they are immediately hit by the smell of bodies being housed together in cells and wards, the noise of voice struggling to be heard from the blocks, the sound of footsteps and the feelings of violence looming around. Literally they are on guard all the time they enter the prison gate since they are locked within prison for around eight hours.

In agreement with this study, dangerousness was the most commonly stated drawbacks of correctional work. Officers work each day with individuals who have previous accounts of violence and are regularly expected to perform jobs that essentially include the thwarting of

prisoners desire and hence the worsening of potentially fierce people.

The correctional officers are almost outnumbered by the prisoners (Chen et al., 2013). Numerous published studies of prison officers have also concurred that the ever existing possibility of inmate violence against correctional officers as a substantial cause of burnout, feelings of threats may stem less from recurrent attacks and more from the awareness that officers face persistent and repeatedly unpredictable likelihood of violence (Petita & Vecchione, 2012)

In a study of 575 New Zealand prison staffs on sources of burnout and their levels of health, factors analysis of the burnout survey revealed six work detailed causes of burnout such as relationship with prisons. Mean burnout totals were meaningfully higher for correctional officers on the "association of prisoners" factor. Many officers reported boredom as a source of burnout citing that interaction with co-workers is limited to roll call activities and their work assignment are routine and primarily intended to maximize security and minimize cost such as that the officers work alone is most of the posts, this also was in agreement with this findings according to (Chen et al., 2013).

This findings is in the line with Higgins (2019) that revealed that 16 prisoners set mattresses on fire in Almitra prison Brazil killing more than 57 inmates most of whom were thought to have asphyxiated in the deadly smoke. The violence was as a result of dispute between rival gays in prison. This exposed correctional officers to danger since some of them sustained injuries and post-traumatic stress disorders when such circumstances arise.

A study by Frank & Hyden (2017) also agreed that being a prison officer is considered one of the hazardous occupations. They are arguably predisposed to job and organizational related hazards as well as psychological and physiological health. They essentially halt prison unrest, disengage prison gangs and safeguard themselves from communicable illness as well. The report further stated that correctional officers are also required to stop fights between

inmates, check their cells, review their meals and protect their colleagues from prisoners' assault. In a survey of 106 correctional officers working in three institutions in Australian correctional system, dangerousness was measured by a five item likert type scale which concurred that dangerousness had a substantial direct effect on burnout (Carson & Thomas 2016).

Also the results were in concurrence with Chen et al., (2013) who established that chronic conditions such as scarce housing, poor housing, poor conditions and oppressive responsibilities are potent stressors instigating burnout among correctional officers.

The kind of job position in a prison facility has been related with burnout as well. Related studies have shown that those in safe custody sections as well as clinical treatment sections reported higher degrees of burnout (Carson & Thomas 2016). More over the study was in line with Frank & Hyden (2017) who revealed that prison officers are predisposed to work and penal institutional related hazards as well as psychological and physiological health.

According to Frank & Hyden (2017) the officers battle with feelings of despair and uselessness have difficulties sleeping at night, have nightmares, hallucinate and are burnout due to post traumatic stress disorders stemming from traumatic work events after which they resort to alcohol or drugs as mechanisms for survival which does not provide any solution to their psychological problems.

The findings further agreed with Andra (2019) that correctional witness prisoners violence and horror, related with dangerous and struggle with occupational stress on a day to day basic amounting to burnout. They are expected to process the trauma and swallow it as part of the job in order to uphold the organizational image since showing weakness would be seen as failure, incompetent, the end of a career or an opening for a hostile inmate to attack. In 2016, correctional officers of Illinois at Cook County jail sustained 500 attacks by prisoners. He further pointed out that it is usual for prison officers to see prisoners murder each other,

participating in large cell fights, setting their cubicles on fire or committing suicide.

Gitau (2013) also agreed that a study conducted by Thandi on the causes and degree of burnout among prison officers in South Africa discovered that 28% of the respondents agreed strongly the view that being predisposed to hazardous inmates can cause burnout. Chen *et al.*, (2012) also concurred that daily contact with inmates and the prison environment are repeatedly reported as causes of burnout, the routine staff-inmate interaction in particular is the most important contributor. Obiora (2012) was also in agreement that inmates do not want to be confined and employ all manner of tricks and manipulations to make their circumstances of imprisonment as relaxed and easy to escape as possible therefore supervising inmates cause burnout to the prison officers.

Okwendi & Ushi (2014) concurred that prison officers face hardened criminals every day in shifts that stretch for long hours in attempt to control thoughts and actions of the inmates. This is also reported to be a cause of burnout since it also involves officers searching their bodies and belongings (which may be unhygienic and infested) for weapons and contraband which may pose as a security threat.

Whiteacre (2013) agreed that prison is a setting comprising a disproportionate danger of predisposition to communicable ailments ranging from airborne illnesses like tuberculosis to blood borne pathogens such as hepatitis B, C and HIV. Inmates crowding in units lead to burnout alongside restrictions of association on study which involves physical constraint during job and rest periods (Carson & Thomas, 2016).

Masango (2016) was also in agreement that there is also risk of unconscious displacement of aggression by inmates as psychological ego defense mechanisms whereby the prison officers may become targets of aggression that is really meant for someone else who is out of site. This study concurred with Obiora (2012) that prisons in Nigeria are in deplorable, unfavorable and harsh conditions, the environments are mostly hot, overcrowded, lice infested and noisy thus

stressful causing burnout to prison officers manning the panel institutions.

This study is also in line with a study which reported that demanding social contacts between correctional officers and prisoners was vigorous and emotionally charged. This relationship is considered as a situation of structural conflicts which causes burnout because one is the keeper and the other is the kept. The kept struggle to compromise the keeper to allow the maladaptive prison subculture to exist and escape to occur yet it is a prison offense which the keeper is required to deter or eliminate at all cost (Torch & Klofas, 2012).

This study is in agreement with Papa (2015) who reported that prison wardens staged a nationwide protest in 2008 citing poor work conditions in Kenyan prisons. In agreement with the correctional prisoners, an investigative report by a committee of specialist led by Honorable Major Retired Marsden Madoka in July 2008 specified a long list of ills such as diseases, filth, incompetence and modern slavery.

Further, the findings of the research concurred with the study by America Addiction Centre (2018) which revealed that prison officers have the second highest death rate of any occupation in America. It further concurred that extreme stress, depression and workplace injuries are some of the daily challenges causing burnout among correctional officers thus influencing them to use drugs and alcohol to get through the dehumanization of their work conditions.

Additionally, this study was in agreement with Oweke (2014) who conducted a study seeking to establish causes of burnout among police officers in Kisumu county, the study sample 451 constable and 12 commanding officers, it was established that work environment was one of the causes of burnout among police officers.

Poor Public Image

Cecil (2018) reported that the public view correctional officer's work and particularly their role as undesirable, bad media attention on staff transgression including sexual assault,

inappropriate relationships, introduction of smuggled goods such as drugs and mobile phones into the prison and arrests by police for non-job related crimes have influenced the public view of correctional officers thereby causing burnout.

The current study is in agreement with Petita & Veccione (2012) who reported that low public acknowledgement and poor public image of the occupation is related to burnout as is demonstrated by the fact that most correctional officers reported that their current job is their second choice. As noted by Ukwendi & Ushi (2014) also agrees with this study that, correctional work was regarded as a job of last option after previous job let-downs and people with higher education were significantly less likely to view correctional work positively or contemplate joining the career due to the impression that it is "dirty work".

The findings in this study also concurred with Chen *et al.*, (2013) who reported that a survey on occupational status revealed that correctional officers ranked below police officers and slightly above blue collar jobs such as carpenter and truck drivers. Also in agreement with Obiora (2012) who argued that prison officers are viewed as common key keepers who are less educated and inferior to the police and other state security organizations. He further pointed out that a study of prison officers of Freetown Central Prison in Sierra Leone found out that majority of the officers were ashamed of their job. Some reported that they cannot put on their uniforms out of prisons because the public will look at them as marginalized and desperate.

Role Ambiguity

Role ambiguity was not reported as a cause of burnout in this study, the findings is therefore contrary to findings by Torch & Clofas (2012) who stated that prison officers are not sure of their roles, unaware of which services they need to delivery to inmates and fault the management for absence of standardized guidelines on treatment of prisoners.

Conclusion

The findings of this study are; 80.4% of the respondents reported that chronic work conditions and job position caused burnout, 35.7% indicated poor public image as causing burnout while 10% of the respondents held to it that burnout was caused by other factors. Role ambiguity was not found to be among the causes of burnout among correctional officers.

It is therefore evident from this study and right to conclude that chronic work conditions and job position causes were the major cause of burnout followed by poor public image. Therefore the correctional officers were demotivated and had very low moral. This negatively affected the job performance leading to poor work output.

Recommendations

The researcher suggests that correctional facility administrators should establish a positive relationship with correctional officers by involving them in certain decision-making procedures. It is important to enhance the overall atmosphere within the organization by implementing measures such as acknowledging and rewarding employees, offering opportunities for advancement, and creating a reliable internal ombudsperson role to address any unjust administrative practices in the institution.

The management of the correctional facilities should ensure friendly and peaceful environments to the officers. They can also ensure fair treatment of the correctional officers and should also ensure a balanced workload among the officers.

They should give adequate praise for the work done. Further, the psychosocial needs of the correctional officers should be identified and addressed by the management team. This will spur the morale of the correctional officers and they will love their work. There is also need for the management of the prisons to create friendly and administratively fair working environment for the correctional officers. This will help in addressing mental health problems of the

correctional officers. There is also need for the management of the prisons not to take punitive actions such as disciplinary or termination of employment to officers suffering from burnout and other related psychological problems but should introduce psychosocial approaches to curb psychological challenges.

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